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ЕЛЕКТРОННІ ПІДРУЧНИКИ І СТУДЕНТИ-МЕДИКИ

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Abstract

The article highlights the types and role of electronic manuals among medical students. Various features of electronic manuals, their properties, storage formats and ease of use are highlighted. Efficiency in use is established. The purpose of the study is to assess the role of electronic manuals among medical students. Research materials. 62 students who studied on the basis of the college of the 1st and 2nd year and the 4th and 5th year of BSMU, specialty "Pharmacy", participated in the study. A questionnaire was prepared for them, regarding the effectiveness of using the electronic manual during the study of the material. 4 groups were created. The 1st group included students of the 4th year of "Pharmacy" of BSMU, the 2nd group - students of the 5th year of "Pharmacy" of BSMU, the 3rd group - students of the 1st year of the College of "Pharmacy" of BSMU, and the 4th group - students of the 2nd year of "Pharmacy" College of BSMU. Research results. According to the survey among medical students, a large percentage of responses were about accessibility and ease of moving EPs. When evaluating the study of educational material from an electronic or paper medium, discrepancies were found among students. Among the 62 students surveyed, 46% (n=28) preferred the paper version while studying the material and 54% (n=34) did not change their decision about the preference for the electronic medium. Conclusion. Therefore, the use of the electronic manual is convenient and accessible for medical students. Using an electronic guide while studying the material is not convenient, so partial preference is given to the paper version.

INTRODUCTION.

As you know, an electronic manual (textbook) (EP) or electronic medium (EN), or electronic educational (scientific) manual (ESP) is an educational (scientific) publication with a systematized presentation of an educational discipline [1,2]. It can be not only a fully covered discipline, but it can be only a certain part, or several topics, which are formed according to state requirements and approved by the academic council of academies (universities, institutes), or officially in the Ministry of Education and Science (MES) [1, 5]. This

EP fully or partially replaces and/or supplements the textbook. The text of such a textbook is presented in electronic form and provides instant transitions from one section (part) to another, which is very convenient for students, teachers and scientists.

The purpose of the study is to assess the role of electronic manuals among medical students.

Research materials. The research involved 62 students who studied in the 1st and 2nd year college and the 4th and 5th year of BSMU majoring in "Pharmacy". A questionnaire was prepared for them, regarding the

effectiveness of using the electronic manual during the study of the material. 4 groups were created. The 1st group included students of the 4th year of "Pharmacy" of BSMU, the 2nd group - students of the 5th year of "Pharmacy" of BSMU, the 3rd group - students of the 1st year of the College of "Pharmacy" of BSMU, and the 4th group - students of the 2nd year of "Pharmacy" College of BSMU.

Main part.

According to the Law of Ukraine "On Education", which stipulates that "an electronic textbook (manual) is an electronic educational publication with a systematic presentation of educational material that corresponds to the educational program, contains digital objects of various formats and provides interactive interaction" [5,8]

There are the following types of EP:

- EP open access through the Internet (can be presented on various scientific (educational) official pages of institutes, academies and universities. They can also be presented on the pages of schools, gymnasiums and lyceums;

- EP for educational use (on the pages of various educational and scientific magazines, sites with various educational directions). [3,4]

Electronic manuals are created for different perception by each student, taking into account his typology.

There are different types of electronic manuals:

1. Static EP;
2. EP with elements of multimedia;
3. Multimedia EP.

Each type of EP has its own principles and functional features.

Static EP, that is, convection electronic educational edition, is based on the following principle: an analogue of a paper textbook in an electronic format. According to its functional features, it can be created in various formats - PDF, DJVU, etc. These formats help to print and transfer information with high quality, without changes to pages and text. However, there is no access to individual fragments, i.e. their changes or addition of additional text.

The combined electronic manual, or EP with multimedia elements, is based on the conversion of a paper textbook into an electronic format using HTML, HTM, etc. formats. This electronic source has multimedia elements that are available in the paper version. Multimedia elements are hyperlinks or links with linear control navigation. This EC in the specified formats allows high-quality printing of individual static fragments and the location of EC on the educational platform, but without access to their editing.

Multimedia EP is a deterministic independent electronic educational publication with a set of logically connected structured didactic units presented in digital form. This manual can be placed on educational platforms. Each student or manager can use the presented material in whole or in part. Easy step-by-step operation of this manual during use and additional equipment with multimedia elements. These elements can be represented by animated and simulated videos,

additionally available sound, etc., which makes it possible to print both individual elements and in full.[6, 7]

There are two types of multimedia EPs:

1. Interactive;
2. Intellectual.

Interactive EP includes a deterministic independent electronic educational publication in various types of creation - text, illustration, animation, tables, audio and video images, simulation, etc.). This makes it possible to place EP on the educational platform of schools, institutes, universities, etc., in order to use it in full or in part. For this type, step-by-step instructions and the presence of control and self-control have been created. This textbook may contain various exercises, problems, assignments and test control. This textbook can be used on different devices and allows access in various hyperlinks on the Internet with the possibility of printing individual fragments of it.

Intellectual EP is a universal independent study guide with a set of general materials, where the teacher creates the structure of the lesson (pairs) with the possibility of rearranging (changing) the placement of educational material. This guide makes it possible to find it on the educational platform in order to use it in full or in part. Any version of the modification, structure, linearity and expansion is inherent to it. Each such guide has an administrator (the representative who created it) on the educational portal or in the social network for the purpose of its full or partial use. This textbook is characterized by step-by-step action, control and self-control, and the presence of additional tasks (exercises) and using it on different devices [9].

Discussion.

While studying in higher educational institutions of the III-IV medical field, each student should have a certain "baggage" of knowledge during the period of study, which will help him to implement his knowledge in practice. It is the medical student who must know a large amount of material, so you need to have a large amount of educational material to study. Since there are many books, authors and researchers who update the research and there are changes in the classification, examination, research and treatment of the disease and the availability of the magnitude of mono- and combined drugs in the student's library, there should be a large number of manuals. As you know, each manual or book is bulky, so there are some difficulties in its transportation and/or finding (as each publisher has a certain number of copies) and obtaining (its price). The electronic manual is an economical, compact, affordable and easily transportable publication that every medical student can afford. A student can download each e-book or manual (or several of them) to an electronic medium and study the educational material without difficulty. In addition, if you have Internet access, you can easily find the necessary educational (scientific) information for studying and supplementing your knowledge.

According to the survey among medical students, a large percentage of responses were about accessibility and ease of moving EPs. (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Evaluation of the use of an electronic manual in the study of educational material among medical students of BSMU

Note. 1st group - students of the 4th year of "Pharmacy" of BSMU,

2nd group - students of the 5th year of "Pharmacy" of BSMU,

3rd group - students of the 1st year of the "Pharmacy" college of the BSMU,

4th group - students of the 2nd year of the "Pharmacy" College of the BSMU,

When evaluating the study of educational material from an electronic or paper medium, discrepancies were found among students. Among the 62 students surveyed, 46% (n=28) preferred the paper version while studying the material and 54% (n=34) did not change their decision about the preference for the electronic medium.

Fig. 2. Evaluation of the use of an electronic manual in the study of educational material among medical students of BSMU

Note. 1st group - students of the 4th year of "Pharmacy" of BSMU,

2nd group - students of the 5th year of "Pharmacy" of BSMU,

3rd group - students of the 1st year of the "Pharmacy" college of the BSMU,

4th group - students of the 2nd year of the "Pharmacy" College of the BSMU.

Conclusion. Therefore, the use of the electronic manual is convenient and accessible for medical stu-

dents. Using an electronic guide while studying the material is not convenient, so partial preference is given to the paper version.

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